

MOTIVATION BENEFITS STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS AND RESULTS OF MATHEMATICAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *In this article, we present episodes from two qualitative research studies. The studies focus on students of different ages and populations and their work on different mathematical tasks. We examine the commonalities in environment, tools, and teacher-student interactions that are key influences on the positive dispositions engendered in the students and their interest and engagement in mathematics.*

Keywords: *formulate strategies, information competence, dispositions, technologies of training, active methods.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье мы представляем фрагменты двух качественных научных исследований. В центре внимания исследований были учащиеся разных возрастов и групп населения, а также их работа над различными математическими задачами. Мы исследуем общие черты в окружающей среде, инструментах и взаимодействии учителя и ученика, которые оказывают ключевое влияние на формирование позитивного настроения у учащихся, а также на их интерес и вовлеченность в математику.*

Ключевые слова: *формулировать стратегии, информационная компетентность, расположение, технологии обучения, активные методы.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada biz ikkita sifatli tadqiqot ishlarining epizodlarini taqdim etamiz. Tadqiqotlar turli yoshdagi va populyatsiyadagi talabalarga va ularning turli matematik vazifalar ustida ishlashiga qaratilgan. Biz atrof-muhit, asboblari va o'qituvchi-talaba o'zaro ta'sirlaridagi umumiyliklarni ko'rib chiqamiz, bu talabalarga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan va ularning matematikaga qiziqishi va jalb qilinishiga ta'sir qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *strategiyalarni shakllantirish, axborot kompetentsiyasi, joylashuv, o'qitish texnologiyalari, faol usullar.*

Introduction

Emphasizing that no country can develop without scientific achievements and innovations in this area, the President said: “Strategies and mechanisms of innovative development of the country are closely linked, first of all, with the effective use of intellectual and scientific-technical potential created in this country. Deepening the integration of science and industry, including science and education, will play an important role in fulfilling this task” [1].

We have developed a framework for mathematics teaching and learning that provides this missing link. It provides teachers and researchers with a conceptual tool that explains how students build the positive attitudes towards mathematics that are necessary to engage in mathematical reasoning. We believe that this approach that can be implemented across the spectrum of mathematics classrooms.

Our research focuses on students who are working collaboratively as they engage in mathematical problem solving. We videotaped students as they engaged in mathematical tasks and then analyzed the reasoning that occurred as they worked to formulate strategies and defend

their solutions. We have found that, although the demographics of the groups of students and the tasks may be different, the reasoning and subsequent understanding that occurs is quite similar.

In this article, we present two episodes from our research, focusing on students of different ages and populations as they work on different mathematical tasks. We then examine the commonalities in environment, tools, and teacher-student interactions that are key influences both on the positive attitudes towards mathematics engendered in the students and on their engagement in mathematics. We hypothesize that these positive attitudes towards mathematics lead to student reasoning and, thus, mathematical understanding [2, 3].

The resulting framework suggests ways that the standards can be implemented in diverse classrooms in order to achieve optimal student engagement and learning. Although the development of our framework began with our data and then was supported by the literature, we begin by presenting the supporting literature in order to give the readers a background for the framework.

In our framework, there are four factors that mediate between elements in the classroom environment, such as tasks, and the development of conceptual understanding through mathematical reasoning. These four factors are autonomy, intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy and positive dispositions towards mathematics. Because the literature concerning all four of these factors is interrelated, we have picked one factor, intrinsic motivation, to organize our discussion around.

All students must be motivated in some way to engage in mathematical activity, however, the nature of that motivation largely determines the success of their endeavor. In particular, students' motivations can be divided into two distinct types: extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation. Extrinsically motivated students engage in learning for external rewards, such as teacher and peer approval and good grades. These students do not necessarily acquire a sense of ownership of the mathematics that they study; instead they focus on praise from teachers, parents and peers and avoiding punishment or negative feedback. In contrast, students who are intrinsically motivated to learn mathematics are driven by their own pursuit of knowledge and understanding. They engage in tasks due to a sense of accomplishment and enjoyment and view learning as impacting their self-images. Intrinsically motivated students, therefore, focus on understanding concepts. Thus, intrinsic, rather than extrinsic, motivation benefits students in the process and results of mathematical activities.

Autonomous students, in attending to problem situations mathematically, rely on their own mathematical facilities and use their own resources to make decisions and make sense of their strategies. Furthermore, through participation in classroom activities, mathematically autonomous students begin to rely on their own reasoning rather than on that of the teacher and thus become arbitrators of what makes sense.

Studies show that teacher support and classroom environments play a crucial role in the development of another source of intrinsic motivation, namely, positive (or negative) dispositions toward mathematics.

Unlike sources of extrinsic motivation, which need to be constantly reinforced, research shows that the common sources of intrinsic motivation are reinforced when students are encouraged to develop their self efficacy. For example, intrinsic motivation helps students succeed at a given learning objective, thereby further developing students' self-efficacy. In general, students are more likely to engage and persist in tasks when they believe they have the ability to succeed. Therefore, intrinsic motivation can lead to an increased willingness to engage in reasoning activities [3].

In summary, research shows that when students are intrinsically motivated to learn mathematics, they spend more time on-task, tend to be more persistent, and are confident in using different, or more challenging, strategies to solve mathematical problems. These qualities of mathematical learners better enable them to actualize the recommendations put forth and to master key mathematical processes in their pursuit of understanding mathematics. Intrinsic motivation, then, is correlated with self-efficacy and positive dispositions towards a conceptual understanding of mathematics, whereas extrinsic motivation results in merely a superficial grasp of the information presented.

In this paper we present results from two research studies investigating students' mathematics learning. The students were engaged, motivated, and, importantly, confident in their ability to offer and defend mathematical solutions; they demonstrated positive dispositions towards mathematics. We identified student behaviors that indicated confidence in mathematics and a high level of engagement. These behaviors include perseverance; the ability to consider more challenging, alternative solutions; and the length of time spent of the task. In the discussion that follows, we analyze the commonalities in the two teaching experiments, and consider how these commonalities may have positively influenced the level of motivation and confidence that students exhibited as they worked on mathematical tasks. In the discussion, we use our findings to define a framework that can be used to inform a teaching practice that will motivate students and encourage student engagement and mathematical understanding [3,4].

Conclusion

In summary, in such a learning environment, students are encouraged to communicate their understandings of the task, and their ideas are valued and respected. This respect engenders students' positive self-concepts in mathematics. At the same time, students become intrinsically motivated to succeed at mathematics. Intrinsic motivation fosters positive dispositions toward mathematics, which, in turn, encourage students to develop self-efficacy and mathematical autonomy as they discuss and share their understandings with their classmates. At the same time, students enjoy doing mathematics and develop ownership of their ideas. In such an environment and with such dispositions, students are more likely to engage in mathematical reasoning and, thus, acquire conceptual understanding.

Our framework and research suggest that with careful attention to developing appropriate and engaging tasks, a supportive mathematical environment, and timely teacher questioning, students can be encouraged to build positive dispositions towards mathematics in all mathematics classrooms. These positive dispositions towards mathematics, in turn, form the ideal conditions for achieving conceptual understandings of mathematics.

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